

Scale the Bound of Probability

Jinxin Wei¹, Zhe Hou²

¹Vocational School of Juancheng, China, wjxabai@163.com

²No.1 High School of Juancheng, China, 1107163828@qq.com

Abstract: There is a problem, in one sample space, there are two events happen as high probability. In the problem, the two events' probability can't above 0.5 because of the sum is 1. More events, less probability. I propose a method that is scale the probability to more than 1 by multiply the distribution probability with $2^{\frac{H(x)}{2}}$. The magnitude is change, but the relative relation of the probability is not change.

Through the scale operation, the probability is larger than before. When two events happen simultaneously after scaling, the joint probability is almost equal the single event's probability before scaling. So in the new bound, it can serve more events to happen simultaneously. The more different of the probability, the less scale it dose. When generate by large language model, we can generate one sentence simultaneously not just one word[4]. The joint probability is higher(in new bound) than before.

Keyword: scale, probability, information entropy, low bound, expected value

1. Introduction

There is a sample space $\{A,B,C\}$ with $P(A)=0.8$, $P(B)=0.1$, and $P(C)=0.1$ because the sum of probability is 1. But when A and B have high probability to happen, the probability distribution maybe $0.49,0.49,0.02$ because the sum is 1. When the sample space is large and more events have high probability to happen, the probability distribution maybe $0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2,0.19,0.01$ because the sum is 1. So the more events have high probability to happen, the less probability assign to event. The magnitude of event probability is small. From the data, we can't know the event has high probability to happen, we only know the probability of event happening is almost the same unless one is small.

2. The scale method

I propose one idea about this problem. If the sum is not 1, we may know the absolute probability of event is high. How to set the sum? The following is the detail. First we calculate the information entropy by the formula

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p(x_i) \log_2 p(x_i) \quad [2] \quad (1)$$

Because $H(X)$ is the bit, so the number it can express is $2^{H(X)}$.

According to Jensen's Inequality[3]

$$E(2^{H(x)}) \geq 2^{E(H(x))} \quad (2)$$

$$2^{E(H(x))} \approx 2^{\frac{H(x)}{2}} \quad [1] \quad (3)$$

So the expected number it can express is $2^{\frac{H(x)}{2}}$.

Finally we multiply the $2^{\frac{H(x)}{2}}$ to the probability of distribution,

that is the scale of probability. The magnitude is change, but the relative relation of the probability is not change.

For example, there is a distribution {0.5,0.5}. Put into the formula, the result is 1.414. The probability multiply 1.414, so the distribution is {0.7,0.7}. For example the distribution is {0.33,0.33,0.33}, put into the formula, the result is 1.732. The probability multiply 1.732, so the distribution is {0.571,0.571,0.571}.

For example the distribution is {0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2}, put into the formula, the result is 2.235. The probability multiply 2.235, so the distribution is {0.447,0.447,0.447,0.447,0.447}.

From the example listed above, the original ratio is 0.33/0.5=0.66, the scaled ratio is 0.57/0.7=0.81, so the probability is larger than before.

When two events happen simultaneously after scaling, the joint probability is almost equal the single event's probability before scaling.

For example $0.7*0.7\approx 0.5$, $0.571*0.571\approx 0.33$, $0.447*0.447\approx 0.2$, so in the new bound, it can serve more events to happen simultaneously.

For example the distribution is $\{0.4,0.3,0.3\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.723. The probability multiply 1.723, so the distribution is $\{0.6892,0.5169,0.5169\}$.

For example the distribution is $\{0.6,0.2,0.2\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.607. The probability multiply 1.607, so the distribution is $\{0.9642,0.3214,0.3214\}$.

For example the distribution is $\{0.77,0.115,0.115\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.418. The probability multiply 1.418, so the distribution is $\{1.09,0.163,0.163\}$.

For example the distribution is $\{0.8,0.1,0.1\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.375, The probability multiply 1.375, so the distribution is $\{1.1,0.1375,0.1375\}$.

For example the distribution is $\{0.9,0.05,0.05\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.217, The probability multiply 1.217, so the distribution is $\{1.095,0.06,0.06\}$.

For example the distribution is $\{0.99,0.005,0.005\}$, put into the formula, the result is 1.031, The probability multiply 1.031, so the distribution is $\{1.02,0.005,0.005\}$.

From the example listed above, the more different of the probability, the less scale it dose.

3.The Application

It can give us more intuitive of probability, especially when several events have high probability to happen. It can put into the formula of softmax, that is $2^{\frac{H(x)}{2}}$ multiply softmax. Then it can classify two or more objects simultaneously, such as one object the model didn't see before, the model may assign high probability to two known objects that are similar to it. When generate by large language model, we can generate one sentence simultaneously not just one word[4]. The joint probability is higher(in new bound) than before.

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